

Our State of Preparedness in Case of Natural Calamities and Disaster

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Abstract:

Azad Jammu & Kashmir is vulnerable to natural hazards which mainly include earthquakes and floods, the state faced a series of natural disasters in last decades. AJ&K receives a substantial amount of rainfall resulting in floods, landslides and avalanches due to heavy snow fall as well. Floods and flash floods to, reiterate are a common features in this post. SDMA is in the process to forestall and manage the same. The aim of the study is to analyze the efficacy of disaster management in state of preparedness in case of natural calamity. The challenges being faced by state disaster management authority in implementation. The study used the Earthquake 2005 and Flood 2014 as a case study to explore the overall scenario of pre and post disaster management of AJ&K. The research is qualitative and exploratory in nature. The data was collected from NDMA, SDMA websites, UN reports etc. The findings shows that institutional incapacities, lack of information, contingency planning, warning and evacuation, risk assessment/prevention as hazard mapping, Hazard and vulnerability assessment, structural and non-structural measures and speedy response are the challenges faced by disaster management in AJ&K.
Key words: Disasters, Preparedness, Mitigation, Vulnerability, Hazards

Introduction

Disasters are taking place continentally with an ever increasing rates happening in all over the world with an increasing rate. Floods, droughts, Earthquakes and many natural hazards endure thousands of deaths, hundreds of thousands of hurts, and caused economic losses each year in the global world(<http://www.cred.be>). Disaster prevention and crisis Management were the topics of interest in the strategy and public administration literatures. It is impossible to stop the Natural disasters but procedures could be adopted to eradicate the prospects of distress. The concept of disaster preparedness embraces actions aimed at improving the safety of life in case of disaster occurrence. Disaster preparedness is a mixture of short- and long-term strategies that diminish the adverse effects of hazards. It is not possible to distinct disaster preparedness from disaster relief and response as they are interconnected.

The most common type of natural disasters are rain and wind storms, floods, earthquakes and volcanic eruptions. In Pakistan most common disasters are floods and earthquakes. Earlier to the earthquake 2005, the response of state to disasters (natural) was carried out mainly on the basis of a ad-hoc through different institution.(Harriat,C 2008). After the 2005 earthquake the national disaster management commission was established which supervises the disaster management authorities at national, provincial and districts level. Responsibilities were assigned by the government of Pakistan for disaster mitigation, preparedness and response and recovery. As a result State disaster management authority was established in AJ&K in 2007. Disaster management authority focus on prevention, preparedness, response and recovery. The flood disaster of 2014 has been taken as a case study to analyze the efficacy of SDMA and have revealed several challenges regarding the national disaster preparedness, the need to strengthen the AJ&K disaster risk reduction mechanism.

Problem Statement

Disasters are natural or man-made phenomenon which has adverse social and economic consequences for the affected population Floods and earthquakes are major disasters in AJ&K. The disaster Preparedness is critical for organizations, households and communities, but they continue to remain unprepared. The loss of life and challenges that were faced aftermath of October 2005 earthquake exhibit the need for formulating appropriate polices and remedial measures to reduce losses from disasters. The government has ranked national

preparedness as a goal. Disaster management authority was established in AJ&K. Disaster Management involves mitigation, preparedness, response, and recovery. The purpose of the study is to analyze the structure and efficacy of disaster management. The study will investigate the gaps between disaster management plans/preparedness and the actual performance of disaster management authority in providing relief.

1.2. Research Questions

The study aims to address the following questions.

- 1- What is the state of efficacy and efficiency of Disaster Management/state of preparedness in case of natural calamities and disasters
- 2- What are the steps taken by Disaster Management in the affected areas to prevent and mitigate response and relief services?
3. What are the factors that hinder the performance of disaster management authority?

1.3 Scope/Significance of Study

During the earthquake 2005, there was no disaster management authority or any other institution except civil defense with limited resources and mandate. Due to lack of organized institutional arrangements, the rescue and relief operation started after 48 hours. The delayed operation increased the loss of life. There is scanty and sketchy research available on institutional incapacities of disaster management System in Pakistan. The natural disaster preparedness is not in place due to un-attention of government to the emergencies. The situation is worse due to lack of institutional capacity and first response to the affected area. Lack of information about the situation further underestimates the event. This study will examine the structure and efficacy of disaster management in AJ&K. The study will identify the factors that hinder the performance of state disaster management authority. The study will fill the knowledge gap in existing literature.

1.4 Literature Review

(Iframboise & Boileo, 2012) indicated that People affected by disaster are defined as those injured, homeless/displaced or requiring immediate assistance. Disasters are categorized as either biological (epidemics) meteorological (storms), hydrological (floods), geo-physical (earthquake) Climatological (droughts).

The notion of community preparedness and emergency planning and their relationship with training, exercise and plan is vital part of management. Effective emergency planning is a continuous process. Hazard vulnerability, structure, emergency facilities and organizational staffing and equipment have the potential for changing over time. The emergency planning process is the mean of identifying, monitoring and responding to these changes. Planning is a part of preparedness. It requires the hazards to which the community is vulnerable, the nature of impact that could occur and geographical areas at risk (Ronald & Michael, 2003).

(Stein, et al.2010) indicated that government at all level makes significant efforts to inform the public about how to prepare for natural disaster. They indicated that desired outcomes can be achieved when emergency planners properly target their efforts to inform the public about how to prepare for natural disaster. Relationship between preparation and outcomes is not intuitively negative raises important consequences for how emergency planners communicate to the public about how to prepare for approaching severe weather.

(Berg, M .G et.al,2011) analyzed that Strategic risk management preparedness efforts should forecast well into future planning is important in mitigating the vulnerability. Different models were used such as Input output econometrics model, has economic impact, Hazus(hazard US) model allows to estimate the potential losses from flood and earthquake, this model suitable to building regional and state .

(Habib ur Rehman et. al.2010).The key problems associated with floods are the lack of proper resources, unreliable and inadequate donations response by international donors, unmet financial pledges, and lack of institutional capacities to mitigate with disaster.

The pressure and release model was developed by Blaikie Canon Davis Wisner in 1994 and modified in 2004 which explained disaster risk in broad perspective. PAR model is internationally accepted for analyzing the progression of vulnerability and safety. The model is based on three components, root cause of vulnerability, dynamic pressure and unsafe condition (ibid)

PAR Model,

Root Causes: These includes inadequate resources, poverty and urbanization that give rise to vulnerability

Dynamic pressure: It converts the root cause into vulnerability. Lack of institutions, education, training, overpopulation and environmental degradation.

Unsafe condition

It focuses on how a population is exposed to risk such as unsafe location unsafe buildings. It is due to poor planning and preparedness.¹Vulnerability and hazards are components of disaster management. Any hazard-flood, earthquake which is a generating vulnerability would lead to disaster. The PAR model is a simple tool for showing people's vulnerability to floods and disasters and how natural disasters take place. In understanding the community vulnerability and disaster risk s PAR model is best one.

1.5 Methodology

This research follows the exploratory approach relying on secondary data. Cooper and Emory (1995) state that data collection mainly depends on the research method adopted for study. The method used in the paper is exploratory research approach. This research is qualitative base and all data are collected from secondary sources NDMA, SDMA reports, research studies, and newspapers, books, reports of disaster management authorities, ERRA etc. The flood 2014 was taken as a case study. The case study allows the exploration of thoughts about complex issues

2- Concepts and Trends in Disaster Management

2.1 Disaster

“A Disaster is result from the mixture of hazards, vulnerability or inadequate measures or capacity to lessen the possible chances of risk. A disaster happens when hazards impact on vulnerable population and causes casualties and distractions”.(cbse.gov.in)

2.3. Disaster Management.

Disaster management includes all the activities which can be taken before, during and after disaster with a purpose to avoid a disaster reduce its impact or recover from its losses.

“**Pre-Disaster measures** “includes planning, warning and evacuation, consolidate preparation for next disasters, other is risk assessment/prevention as hazard mapping, vulnerability assessment, structural and non-structural measures)”. www.issai.org.

“**Post-Disaster Measures includes** immediate interventions rescue, security, food, water, clothing, shelter, medication, medical and trauma care. Rehabilitation (Restorations of basic services and functions, Reconstruction”(Pathriage Chaminda,2011)

2.4 Disaster Management Cycle

The disaster Management cycle exhibits the on-going process .The disaster management cycle comprises of policies and plans. The mitigation and preparedness stages occurred for enhancement of disaster management in anticipation of a disaster. When disaster occurs, different organizations specifically the philanthropist organizations play their roles and involved in the immediate response and recovery.

(Habib-ur-Rehman, et al. 2013) The positive efforts by Govt. “dissemination of flood warnings through media (internet, TV, Radio and Newspapers), effective response of the Nation including the universities towards rehabilitation and relief, effective response of district management and army towards evacuation. Finally it is emphasized that there is urgent need to bridge the gaps between formulated flood plans (reports) and their effective implementation to the satisfaction of the end users”.

2.5 Disaster Management Plan

2.5.1 Prevention

“Identify and minimize the risks and hazards in the area. Carry out a building inspection and alter factors which constitute a potential hazard. Install automatic fire detection and extinguishing systems, and alarms”. Make safety arrangements. Special precautions especially in building renovation”.(www.nasa.gov,webworld.unesco.org)

2.5.2. Preparedness

It includes the contingency planning, warning, evacuation etc. How to plan and make strategy ,Develop a plan, update it, establish disaster response team, Disaster training response techniques, Prepare and keep an up-to-date set of documentation, Preparations for funding emergency requirements.

2.5.3. Phase 3: Response

When disaster strikes. Efforts to lessen the hazards include scarcity of food, water and medicine etc. Follow established emergency procedures for raising the alarm, make safe sites and evacuating people, make an initial assessment of of the damage, and assess the required services, equipment, and supplies .

2.5.4 Phase 4: Recovery

It includes the rehabilitation reconstruction. Restoration of basic services, Returning the community to the back to reestablish both the disaster site and the damaged materials to a usable form. Provide temporary houses, grant, medical facility etc.

2.6 Disaster Impact

Risk Management

Preparedness
Mitigation
Prevention

Crisis Management

Response
Rehabilitation
Reconstruction

2.7. Disaster Preparedness

The public policy makers and social scientists focus on disaster: mitigation, preparedness, response, and recovery. According to the National Research Council (NRC 2006), the basic areas of disaster research include: pre-disaster research and vulnerability analysis and mitigation; and post-disaster emergency response and recovery. “Preparedness overlaps with both the pre and post disaster effects. Preparedness consisting of

measures that enable different organizations, individual communities, household and societies to respond efficiently and recover rapidly when disasters occur". Preparedness efforts guaranteeing that the resources required for responding effectively are in place, and those who respond know about the usage of resources. The events that are generally linked with disaster preparedness comprise of developing planning processes to ensure readiness; framing disaster plans; storage of important resources for effective response; and developing skills to ensure effective performance. The concept of disaster preparedness includes actions intended at improving safety of life.

2.8. Disaster Management in Pakistan/AJ&K

The structure of Pakistan disaster management has changed since 2005. Earlier to the 2005 earthquake state response of state to natural disasters was carried out temporarily. The major actors comprised the emergency relief cell, the federal flood commission and the Pakistan meteorological department and federal flood commission. It was realized that earthquake required a more organized and enormous relief response. Due to this purpose in Oct 2005 federal relief commission was established to manage the huge operation of rescue and relief. It was required to rationalize operation of relief in collaborations with NGOs, provincial government, Red Crescent relevant ministries, and other agencies and the army as well. In support of re-building efforts, the ERRA was established in 2005 in collaborations with international institutions, international organizations and with other international agencies .In 2006 Govt. absorbed the Federal Relief commission into ERRA which carry on the reconstruction efforts in country..

The national disaster management commission leads over disaster management authorities at national, provincial and districts level which heralds a different level of the responsibilities for disaster mitigation, preparedness and response. The NDMA was established in 2007. The NDMA is a key for disaster preparedness and response. NDMA containing the civil defense, armed forces, provincial DDMA civil society, philanthropic agencies, rescue and relief operations and recovery and rehabilitation response.

Analysis of the State of preparedness in Pakistan/AJ&K

The study analyzed the Earthquake (2005)/Flood (2014) disasters in AJ&K. The state of preparedness at government level was analyzed. The study analyzed the efficiency of disaster management authority, the preparedness (plans) and challenges faced by disaster management authority in PAK/AJ&K.

3.1 Hazards in AJ&K

Earthquakes, Landslides, Floods, River Erosion, Glacial Lake, outbursts, Avalanches, Storms, Droughts, Heavy Rains, Epidemics, Lightening

3.2 Pre-earthquake arrangements

Crisis Management Cell of the Ministry of Interior was charged with the Responsibility of Coordination of Emergencies, The Civil Defence Organisation was Responsible for Maintaining Normal Life Activities/ its Restoration without delay, if disturbed due to Enemy Action or Natural Calamities. The focus of the above Institutional Arrangements remained Primarily on Post Disaster Response. The Relief Commissionerate System in terms of the Calamity Act of 1958 meant for providing Relief Assistance. Under the 1973 Rules of Business, the subject of Disaster Relief was assigned to the ERC of the Cabinet Division (Pakistan).

3.3 Post-earthquake

Federal Relief Commission (FRC) at Federal level, Crisis Management Cell (CMC) at State level, Camp Management Organization (CMO) at State level. The high Magnitude of 8th October, 2005 disastrous earthquake highlighted the exposure and vulnerability of the state machinery of Pakistan and AJ&K

towards such catastrophes carrying vast socio economic implications. There was lack of any organized response and emergency services. The lack of preparedness caused a massive destruction in the country. Consequently, “State Disaster Management Authority” was established with legitimate cover for this purpose in 2007. Establishment of Relief, Disaster Management & Civil Defense Secretariat in 2010.

Constitution of the Secretariat;

- State Disaster Management Authority, Civil Defense Department
- Relief Commissioner, One stop shop for integrating Disaster Risk Reduction Measures (DRRM) into public policy guidelines.

3.4 Disaster Management Commission

Headed by the Honourable Prime Minister of AJ&K

Members

Leader of the Opposition, Senior Minister in the Cabinet, Minister for Works, Communication, Reconstruction & Rehabilitation, Minister for Health, Minister for Social Welfare, Minister for Civil Defence, Chief Secretary AJ&K, Senior Member Board of Revenue, AJ&K, Inspector General of Police, AJ&K, Secretary Finance, AJ&K, Representative of Civil Society or any other person appointed by the Prime Minister AJ&K

Functions

Make Policies and guidelines for smooth streamlining of Disaster Risk Reduction in AJ&K. Allocate resources for the envisioned infrastructure framework.

3.5 State Disaster Management Authority

Chairman Chief Secretary GOAJ&K

Secretariat Relief, Disaster Management & Civil Defence

Members

- Secretary Finance, Secretary Electricity, Secretary Agriculture & Animal Husbandry, Secretary Health, Secretary Social Welfare, Secretary Local Government & Rural Department, Secretary Law, Justice, Parliamentary Affairs & Human Rights, Commissioner Relief, Director General, Civil Defence, Additional Secretary (Home), Divisional Commissioners, Muzaffarabad, Mirpur & Poonch

Functions

- Monitor/integrate/enforce Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) measures, Prepare strategies, Streamline institutions, pool resources, build capacity, Integrate monitoring standards, Enable/establish rapid response schemes/force to reduce AJ&K's exposure/vulnerability, Advocate integration of DRR measures into future socio-economic development policies

3.6 District Disaster Management Authority

The district disaster management authority is headed by deputy commissioner and consists of following members

Members

SSP/SP of the District, District Health Officer, Assistant Director Civil Defence, Member of Legislative Assembly from the respective areas. DDMA Serve as front line flag post for combating emergency situations and resource activator / mobilizer.

Functions

Formulate district Disaster Risk Management (DRM) plan, Coordinate and monitor the implementation of district DRM plan, Continuously monitor the hazards, risks, and disaster threats and coordinate with vulnerable population, Prepare guidelines for mitigation, preparedness, and response as well as for risk reduction. The operative framework as follow:

The operative framework of disaster management in AJ&K consists of State disaster commission which is headed by prime minister who is the chairman while ministers, opposition and civil society representatives are the members of SDMC.

The coordination framework based on SDMC to Tehsil level bodies to prepare, response and recovery in case of disaster occurrence.

Responsive Framework

The Response framework of Disaster Management at national, State and local level is as follows

Identify training needs and conduct training and awareness programs, Setup, maintain, review & upgrade district level early warning and communication systems, Mobilization and coordination with other agencies for interventions at the time of emergencies, Mobilize needed financial and other resource for disaster risk management, Identify buildings and places as evacuation sites or relief centers in case of disaster. Establish stocks of relief and rescue materials ensure preparedness, Keep linkages with the SDMA & the Relief Department

3.7. Efficacy of SDMA/Milestones achieved

Promulgation of AJ&K Disaster Management Act (2008), Establishment of SDMA through notification in official gazette, 24hr operatives of SDMA/SEOC have been established as per the National Disaster Management Framework (NDMF), Winter and Summer/Monsoon contingency planning in consultation with NDMA, stakeholders and line departments, AJ&K State Disaster Management Plan, Establishment of Disaster Risk Management Coordination Forum, involving Govt. functionaries, NGOs and INGOs, Establishment of State Emergency Operation (SEOC) Centre

3.8. State emergency operation center

The SEOC shall perform following functions:

Planning for Disaster mitigation, preparedness, response and recovery, Monitor Developing Threats, Organize field assessments and disseminate incident and loss/damage information through DDMA, Coordinate resources with GoAJK, NDMA, UN Agencies, INGOs, NGOs for emergency requirements, Control and manage State level emergency operations through DDMA and other stake holders, Ensure that the Government and the communities are alert and are kept informed of evolving situation.

3.9. Measures Taken By SDMA

SDMA website launched, SEOC established and now operative 24/7 as per the National Disaster Management Framework (NDMF), WFP supported Flospan (300 MT capacity) erected in Muzaffarabad and Neelum. Approved for Hattian & Bagh, Acquisition of 15 Kanal Land for Construction of Central Warehouse, Completion of office, accommodation for 1122 district HQ & Civil Defence at Mirpur and Kotli,

Installation of Early Warning System for Earth Quakes (SECTY Equipment's), School safety pilot project completed including mock drills in 37 schools covering 5000 students, Monsoon contingency planning in consultation with NDMA, stakeholders and line departments & its monitoring & review, Disbursement of Rs. 548 million for compensation to the affectees through WATAN card (CDC), Islamic Relief, PRCS, AJKRSP, Malteser International, PRDP and WFP supported advocacy campaigns and trainings for volunteers and local communities, DRM Awareness Campaigns, Creation of Disaster Risk Management Coordination Forum, involving all stakeholders, Establishment of Gender & Child Cell (GCC).

3.10. Upcoming projects

Establishment of Flospan (300 MT capacity) in remaining six districts, Establishment of Central Ware House (3000 MT Capacity), Establishment of EOCs at Divisional Level, District wise Multi-Hazardous risk mapping and mainstreaming through DRM projects, Setting up archive/data bank for research and development purpose, Project proposed for establishment of Landslides Management Cell in SDMA.

3.11. Role of emergency services

²To maintain a state of preparedness to deal with emergencies and provide timely response, rescue and emergency medical treatment to the victims; Establishment of rapid communication system exchange of information, To arrange for a universal toll free emergency dial-in-number to be used throughout Azad Kashmir; Provide safe transportation to the victims, To establish community emergency response teams; Providing of training to rescuers, volunteers and other private persons.

3.12. Mock Exercises

Rescue 1122 mock exercises in Muzaffarabad has already been carried out on 8th October, 2013 in order to ensure effectiveness of human resource, equipment and operational plans in case of road traffic accidents, medical and trauma Emergencies, fire and collapse of buildings, other natural and man disasters in timely manners.

Awareness regarding building codes, Earthquake Safe Building Construction, Emergency Exit Staircase, Fire Alarm System, Fire Extinguishers on each floor, Fire Hose Cabinet near Emergency Exit Staircase, Sprinkler System for Commercial Buildings, Hydrant Point outside the building for fire, Rescue Service, Building Evacuation Plan displayed at prominent places, Enforcement of building safety codes, Enforcement of Building Safety By-laws by: Concerned Development Authority. Respective Local Government, Fire Drills to be initiated by Rescue 1122.

Municipal Corporation.

Monitoring of building Inspection & Monitoring of Major Buildings, Hotels etc. by joint teams of experts from Rescue 1122 and other relevant departments. Community Training & Volunteer Enrollment Program Launching of Community Training and Volunteer Enrollment Program to establish Community Emergency Response Teams. Training of officials of Government & Private Organizations.

3.14. Liaison with Hospitals

Fool Proof liaison with Emergency Departments of the Hospitals in all Districts has been established through effective wireless communication system operational round the clock. Timely information to the emergency department of the Hospitals in case of major emergency in the city.

3.15. Emergency Services Academy

- Staff of Emergency Services Rescue 1122 is professionally trained and passed out from Punjab Emergency Services Academy Rescue 1122 Lahore.
- Training has been provided on international standards to the staff of Emergency Services Rescue 1122.

3.16. Progress of Rescue 1122 Muzaffarabad in three months

Installation of three Emergency Toll free numbers with short code of (1122), Connecting Wireless communication system of Rescue 1122 with Police wireless communication system, Conducting of physical and operational training Course for Rescue 1122 staff Muzaffarabad, Fabrication of two Ambulances according to the international standard, Carried out Public Awareness activities about Emergency services Rescue 1122, Launching Ceremony of Rescue 1122 by the Honorable Prime Minister Azad Jammu & Kashmir on 8th October 2013.

3.17. Flood 2014- Case Study and preparedness Analysis

The total human private losses in flood 2014 were 481 million while infrastructure losses are 10075.70 M. The main causes were as follows;

- The causes of flood are :Ineffective enforcement of Forest & Environmental Laws,
- Inadequate Mitigation Plans, Reforestation & Afforestation Projects, Revamping of Forest Laws, Poor implementation of Land Use & Master Plans in Urban & Semi Urban areas, No Plan for Climate Change Adaptation Measures

3.17.1. Inadequate flood protection arrangements

“The protection works arrangements to keep the human settlements, properties and crops etc. Situating along the threatening Nallahs, landslide areas and areas exposed to flash flood are quite inadequate in terms of extending safeguards to vulnerable populations against the flood hazards”. (www.ndma.gov.pk)

3.17.2. Inadequate flood early warning arrangements

“The scientific early warning system and alert warning issuance and communication system is weak. No arrangements are in place to forewarn vulnerable communities of flash flooding and land sliding across the mountainous regions. Moreover, Community EW mechanisms has remained largely ineffective during the 2010 floods, 2012 and 2013 flash flood due to temporary suspension of cellular and landline telecommunication networks”.

3.17.3. Encroachments

“Most of the losses (life and property) during 2010 floods and Monsoon 2012, 2013 were occurred as a result of unchecked massive encroachments and intrusion of population along river banks of Neelum and Jhelum rivers as well as different Nallahs, partly along the flood prone hill torrents. Moreover, blocked and heavily encroached drainage systems of settlements also played a major role in inundation and consequent destruction”. (www.ndma.gov.pk)

3.18. Preparedness Analysis

While preparation of monsoon plan SDMA adopts gross root level approach and involved the district administration, Line departments and all other stake-holders by figuring out their well-defined roles and responsibilities through planning and response phases. The consultation and coordination meetings were carried out with DDMA's and other stake-holders at each Divisional Headquarters. The concerned departments were

provided the prescribed format and advised to submit their monsoon contingency plan while identifying their strengths and gaps in order to efficiently cop with any given situation.

The forthcoming Monsoon Contingency Planning of 2014 has been prepared while keeping the worst case scenario in mind and taking the resource mapping and strengths and weaknesses at all tiers of State level into consideration.

3.18.1 Contingency Plan 2014

The District-wise Contingency Plans disseminated in early July. The main features of contingency plan are; Resource mapping (financial resources, ambulances, evacuation places and health facilities etc), Identification of vulnerable sites, identification and deployment of heavy machinery, availability of tents, blankets, medicines, vaccines and food items etc. establishment of central and field emergency control rooms.

3.18.2 Objectives of Moonsoon Plan

The following are the major objectives for the Monsoon Contingency Plan:-

- “To enhance effectiveness and well-timed emergency response.
- To ensure that emergency response is coordinated through clarification of goals, strategies, roles and responsibilities.
- To anticipate and overcome difficulties.

To strengthen response coordination between State Government Departments, District Governments, humanitarian organizations (UN Agencies INGOs/NGOs).”(www.ndma.gov.pk)

3.18.3 Response

Timely Evacuation of population from endangered areas in Mirpur and Bhimber Districts, Rescue of 3000 trapped and stranded people in Districts Bagh, Poonch, Kotli, & Mirpur, Immediate restoration of road communication, power and water supply by State departments, NHA and WAPDA, Availability of wheat flour and medicines ensured in affected areas, NDMA urgently provided tents, blankets and plastic mats.

PM AJK constituted “Emergency Response Committee” for daily monitoring, as under:

Chief Secretary, Chairman, Senior Member BOR Member, Secretary LGRD Secretary SDMA, Secretary Food , Secretary C&W, Secretary Electricity, Commissioner Mzd, DIG Headquarter, DIG Special Branch

Emergency Response Committee daily held meetings during the critical phase for supervising relief efforts including:(i) Provision of tents, (ii) Opening of roads, (iii) Restoration of electricity

(iv) Availability of wheat flour (v) Provision of medicines, Daily meetings were held to monitor the response activities. Prime Minister also visited the affected areas.

3.18.4. Recovery Need Assessment

Initial assessment by the District Authorities carried out: A committee constituted for assessment of losses to private property:

Tehsildar is the chairman while Naib Tehsildar, Gardawar Circle, patwari are the members.

3.19. Issues and challenges

- “DDMA Muzaffarabad has gathered information with respect to potential flood affected families throughout the district totaling to 300 families”.
- DDMA Muzaffarabad lacks necessary financial and physical resources to deal with the emergencies. For this purpose Rs. 1.00 million may be provided as revolving fund to cope any emergency or forthcoming monsoon emergency operation requirements.
- NHA, AJK Communication and Works department and other concerned agencies should be held equipped and responsible for clearance of roads from Kohala to Chakothi, Muzaffarabad to Neelum and other link roads”.
 - Weak disaster management coordination mechanism
 - Lack of political support
 - Lack of awareness and non-awareness by key stakeholders
 - Overdependence on the donors
 - Lack of knowledge and skill among local communities about the disaster preparedness. Now the paradigm shift through adoption of prevention/mitigation and preparedness approach in place of traditional emergency and response oriented approach
 - Lack of institutional and legal arrangements
 - Lack of Hazard and vulnerability assessment
 - Disaster Risk management planning
 - Community and local level training
 - Mainstreaming disaster risk reduction into development

Conclusion

The history of Azad Jammu & Kashmir bears witness to the fact that state has suffered immensely due to natural and human induced disasters which have adversely affected the economic growth as well as public infrastructure. The state disaster management authority with the support of NDMA has developed the state disaster risk management plan every year State faces a major disasters resulting in heavy economic and human losses .During the earthquake 2005 there was no disaster Management Authority or any other institutions except civil defense with limited scope and mandate which had helped or guided the people. There was no reliable coordination Centre, having information system, data base, SOPs and trained search and rescue teams. There was no network of NGOs and INGOs. Due to these reasons many people lost their lives during and after the earthquake because of the delayed rescue and relief operation and death toll raised to 78000 people. In addition to that people had to bear the loss of property of Rs. 600 billion and process of rehabilitation and reconstruction is still in progress. The flood 2010 and 2014 has also devastating effect on the lives and properties. The establishment of SDMA after earthquake 2005. The mandate of SDMA is to establish linkage with line department and all stakeholders to cope with disaster. SDMA continues to emphasize upon the contingency planning process as a preparedness measure for response to natural hazards. Keeping in view, the contingency plans for past three years, the upcoming 2014 monsoon contingency plan is prepared. The State level contingency plan is formulated for translating recommendations from district administration and other stakeholders into action. It focuses on planning for hazards to identify and analyze related risks for not just their humanitarian impacts but also associated adverse effects on private and public infrastructure, and to define roles and responsibilities of diverse stakeholders for preparedness and adequate response. Thereby ensuring coordination and optimizing the use of resources among agencies in the field while complementing each other's efforts with appropriate linkages and better coordination to support actions along lines of command. The findings shows that Re-structuring, Strengthening and Capacity Building of SDMA, adaptation of Climate Change measures are important for effective planning. Early forecast proper assessment Effective enforcement of Forest and Environmental Laws, Aggressive enforcement of building codes and land use planning. The major problems faced by SDMA are the lack of financial resources, irregular and inadequate donation, lack of

institutional capacities, poor warning system, and lack of proper assessment. The state of preparedness needs much to be desired.

Recommendations

- The government should provide funds for capacity building of community and line department so that they may be able to combat hazards converting in to disaster
- Re -Structuring of NDMA and its implications. after 18th amendment
- Flood forecasting is important measure to provide relief, Flood warning centers must be established
- Proper land-use planning and effective implementation of planning
- Enhance tree plantation
- Need of better coordination among all stakeholders
- Need of flood zoning laws to demarcate the areas that is liable to be effected by floods
- Proper planning and consistent efforts towards implementation
- The SDMA should bring all stakeholders under one umbrella
- Develop a monitoring mechanism for relief, rehabilitation and reconstruction process by involving the community and concerned line department
- Provide training to the local community for prevention and preparedness
- To bridge the gap between the planned and actual implementation
- Utilize local based disaster risk management
- Proper environmental management and action plan
- Pre and post disaster management must be introduced as a compulsory subject in universities, colleges and schools
- Need to focus on Disaster Management training and sensitization
- SDMA needs to establish committees by involving Natural resource related department, research institutes, relevant NGOs and INGOs to generate and maintain environmental database

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